

A study on alkali activated green binder from blended fly ash and GGBS

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Abstract:

One of the main building blocks, concrete, has cement as its primary element. Due to both the hydration process used to create ordinary cement and the increased usage of concrete, there has been a rise in the evolution of greenhouse gases, most notably carbon dioxide. Approximately 3% more cement is produced each year. During cement production, due to the decarbonization of limestone in the kiln and burning of fossil fuels, 1000 kg of cement releases around 1000 kg of CO₂ into the environment. In order to reduce greenhouse gas evolution, Alkali activated binder from fly ash, has been attempted. The alkaline liquids are incorporated to react with the fly ash to form the said zel. Flyash, which is the byproduct of burning coal in a thermal power station, is often recognised as a troublesome solid waste. Each year more than 375 million tonnes of flyash are generated throughout the world whose disposal cost is around \$20 to \$40 per tonne. Fly ash is termed as a pozzolan. Pozzolan is said to be a substance containing aluminous and siliceous material that forms binder in presence of alkali. Natural mineral ores like lime and aluminium are getting depleted due to increased usage in conventional cement manufacturing.

The performance of Alkali activated mortar has been studied. The study shows that alkali activation of pozzolanic materials like fly ash / GGBS along with conventional sand provides high compressive strength even higher than conventional cement mortar. A synthesizing parametric study on strength of such mortar have been done. Various combinations of alkali activation are tried. This compound constitutes of locally collected industrial flyash from power plant (CESC-Haldia), Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS) from Owndust Co. Ltd. and fine aggregate (conventional local sand) with sodium Hydroxide – Na (OH) and Sodium Silicate - Na₂SiO₃. In each case, the test specimens were subjected to heat curing (24 -48 hours at 850C). Finally, the specimens were tested in compressive testing machine and test results are provided. It may be noted here that use of conventional cement is totally avoided from the consideration of Green technology and waste management.

Keywords: Flyash, GGBS, alkali activators, green binder, mortar

1. Introduction

About 25 billion tonnes of CO₂ are released worldwide each year from various sources. About 8% of all CO₂ emissions are caused by the production of Portland cement. The CO₂ emissions of the cement sector are being reduced significantly. The patterns of land use, regional water management, and ambient air quality are all impacted by limestone mining. Thus, one of the key causes of the significant environmental effect still stands. During cement manufacturing the main issues faced by the industries is dust emissions. The industry deal with millions of tonnes of dry material which escapes into the environment as dust. Even if just 0.1% of the dust emission makes it to the atmosphere, it still has a negative impact on the ecosystem. There is a serious issue with fugitive emissions, and neither a strong economic motive nor

tighter regulatory pressure exist to reduce emissions.

A byproduct of iron blast furnaces is ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS). Calcium aluminates and silicates make up the majority of GGBS, a nonmetallic, granular, glassy substance. When processed to fewer than 45 microns from a coarser, friable structure that resembles popcorn, slag has a specific surface area of 400 to 600 m²/kg (Blaine). Cement and GGBS have nearly identical chemical compositions. GGBS is widely combined with Portland cement as a low-cost filler to increase the workability, density, durability, and resistance to alkali-silica reaction of the concrete.

Geopolymer concretes (GPC), which can employ all grades and classes of Fly Ash and GGBS when the right process technology is used, have emerged as an alternative yet potentially economic application of FA and GGBS in the building sector. As a result, there is a good likelihood that these waste materials' stocks will be decreased.

An overview of Geopolymers/Alkali Activated Composites

Geopolymer binder may be considered as a third-generation binder. To activate aluminosilicate materials, alkaline activators such as sodium hydroxide (NaOH), potassium hydroxide (KOH), sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃), and potassium silicate (K₂SiO₃) are generally utilized. KOH has a higher amount of alkalinity compared to NaOH. NaOH has been found to have a greater ability to release silicate and aluminate monomers, though. NaOH solution's molarity was adjusted between 8M, 10M, 13M, and 16M. Sand from the area can be used as the fine aggregate. The qualities of geopolymer concrete can be optimized for a particular purpose by using the suitable raw material selection, combination, and processing design. Even though different aluminosilicate sources produce geopolymers with many of their physical properties appearing to be identical, these geopolymers have quite varied microstructures and chemical properties.

Table 1: typical characteristics of geopolymer mixtures, dealt with different researchers.

Researchers	Density (kg/m ³)	Molarity (M)	Slump (mm)	MOE (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Activator / binder ratio	Curing temperature and time
Hardjito et al.	2330 – 2430	10 – 16	60 – 215	23–31	0.12–0.16	0.35–0.4	60 – 80 °C for 24 hours
Jimenez et al.	-	8 & 12.5	-	10.7–18.4	-	0.4 & 0.55	85°C for 20 hours
Sofi et al.	2147 – 2408	-	-	23–39	0.23–0.26	0.45–0.59	23°C till testing
Diaz-loya et al	1890 – 2371	14	100-150	1.9–42	0.08–0.22	0.4–0.94	60 °C for 72 hours
Pan et al.	1876 – 2555	8	-	11.2–41.2	0.15–0.19	0.4–0.65	60°C for 24 hours

Geopolymer is created when solid aluminosilicate powder reacts with hydroxide or silicates of alkali. At extremely alkaline circumstances, polymerization occurs when reactive aluminosilicate is swiftly broken down and free [SiO₄]²⁻ and [AlO₄]⁻ tetrahedral units are released in solution. The following reactions take place during geopolymerization:

Ingredients of Geopolymer/ Alkali Activated Composites Concrete

The two main elements of geopolymers are the source materials and liquid alkalis. The availability, pricing, kind of application, and end-user demand are all variables that influence which raw materials are utilised to make geopolymers. Fly ash from a power plant (CESC-Haldia) and ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS) from Owndust Co. Ltd. are both used in the current investigation. Sodium or potassium is the most common base for alkaline beverages. A mixture of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) or potassium hydroxide (KOH) and silicates of sodium or potassium is the most common alkaline liquid used in geopolymerization. The Si/Al ratio must be kept as high as feasible. Analytical grade NaOH pellets are used to create the NaOH solution. Before the concrete is made, the alkaline liquid is held for 24 hours.

Test Specimen Casting and Curing

The same methods used to make traditional cement concrete are also employed to prepare geopolymer concrete. First, dry mixing was done with the fly ash and the aggregates. Then extra water was added along with the alkaline liquid (if required to have workable concrete). After adding the liquid mixture to the dry ingredients, the mixture was stirred for an additional 4 to 5 minutes to create a cohesive, usable consistency. The freshly prepared concrete can be handled for up to 30 minutes without exhibiting settling concerns. In the following step, new concrete was cast and compacted in conventional cube moulds measuring 70.6 mm by 70.6 mm by 70.6 mm. To determine if fresh concrete is workable, the standard slump test/Flow test is employed.

Generally, heat curing is essential if the source material is Fly ash but water curing may be made if GGBS is blended with Fly ash. Geopolymer concrete's compressive strength is influenced by both curing temperature and curing time. Longer curing times improve polymerization, resulting in higher compressive strength. Numerous investigations have been done to find out how different curing conditions affect the characteristics of geopolymer concrete. Observations show that curing temperatures for full geopolymerization ranged from 65 to 85 degrees Celsius. The current investigation takes into account curing at 85 °C for 48–96 hours.

Experimental results

	Fly Ash (%)	GGBS (%)	Sand (%)	NaO ₂ (%)	SiO ₂ (%)	Curing Hours	Compressive Strength (MPa)
Mix-1	50	0	50	14	8	48	35.8
Mix-2	40	10	50	14	8	48	23.4
						72	29.2
						96	32.6
Mix-3	35	15	50	14	8	48	21
						72	27.9
						96	30.4
Mix-4	30	20	50	14	8	48	18.6
						72	22.1
						96	22.5

*Source material / Sand – by weight

Fig. 1. Variation of compressive strength for 48Hrs curing

Fig. 2. Variation of compressive strength for 72Hrs curing

Fig. 3. Variation of compressive strength for 96Hrs curing

Conclusion

According to the test results, Alkali activated binders provide concrete with more strength and durability than traditional cement concrete, and that they have a significant chance of becoming a popular building material in the future. This is because they are not only environmentally friendly but also have superior engineering qualities. India's environmental situation makes it necessary to develop suggestions for using geopolymer concrete technology in practical applications, like precast concrete products and waste encapsulation. Due to their lower internal energy (between 20% and 30% less) and essentially zero CO₂ emissions, the new composites can be seen as being more environmentally benign from a Green technology standpoint. Due consideration must be given to more useful practical application.

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